

observed during July and August. The minimum differences reached approximately $-35 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ during the middle of the warm season. These results indicate that climate warming increases early snowmelt contribution while reducing water availability during late summer due to depletion of seasonal snow reserves and reduced glacier melt contribution.

The coefficient of variation analysis demonstrated substantial changes in runoff variability between the two climatic periods (Fig. 1). Higher variability was mainly observed during transitional hydrological seasons, particularly in spring and autumn. In the recent climatic period, coefficient of variation values exceeded 40–50% during several periods of the year, indicating increasingly unstable runoff conditions. The largest differences in variability were observed around days 50 and 250 of the hydrological year, suggesting stronger fluctuations in river discharge under changing climatic conditions. These results indicate that climate change affects not only mean river discharge but also the stability and predictability of seasonal runoff regimes.

Trend analysis using the Mann–Kendall test revealed statistically significant seasonal trends in daily runoff during 1965–2020 (Fig. 2). Positive trends were mainly detected during April and May, where increasing discharge corresponds to intensified and earlier snowmelt processes. In contrast, statistically significant negative trends dominated during July and August, indicating decreasing summer runoff. Sen’s slope values showed the strongest positive trends during spring and the strongest negative trends during the middle of summer. The concentration of statistically significant trends during the warm season confirms substantial seasonal redistribution of runoff under ongoing climate warming conditions [4].

Overall, the obtained results demonstrate considerable transformation of the hydrological regime of the Pskem River during recent decades. Earlier runoff formation and declining summer discharge may create increasing pressure on downstream water management systems, particularly for irrigation and hydropower sectors that depend on stable summer water availability. The identified seasonal runoff redistribution and increasing variability are consistent with hydrological changes observed in other glacier- and snow-fed river basins of Central Asia under climate warming conditions [5].

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ASSESSMENT OF CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON INFLOW TO THE KARAJ DAM (CASE STUDY: IRAN, KARAJ DAM)

Abstract. In this study, the role of climate change and its impacts on temperature and precipitation in the future period on the inflow to the Karaj Dam was evaluated using the LSTM and LSTM-FHO simulation methods. Inflow data, along with hydrometric and meteorological variables, were analyzed during the training and validation periods, and the best combination of predictor

variables was determined based on the RMSE, MAPE, R^2 , and Nash indices. To simulate the impacts of climate change, three climate models, including BCC-CSM2, MRI-ESM2, and CNRM-CM6-1, were selected, and downscaling was performed using the LARS-WG model under three greenhouse gas emission scenarios: SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5. The results indicated that the average temperature is expected to increase, while precipitation is projected to decrease. Consequently, the inflow to the Karaj Dam during the 2021–2050 period is expected to decrease by approximately 16% compared to the baseline period. This reduction in inflow is accompanied by increased uncertainty in future periods and may have significant impacts on regional water resource supply.

Key words: climate change, Karaj Dam, Inflow Simulation, LSTM Model, LARS-WG Downscaling

Introduction. Climate change is considered one of the most significant challenges of the present century in water resources management [5]. Rising air temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns, increased intensity of extreme events, and shifts in runoff timing have caused many watersheds to experience serious fluctuations in surface water resources. This issue is particularly important in countries such as Iran, where a large portion of the territory is located in arid and semi-arid regions, as reductions or instability in surface flows can significantly affect the supply of water for domestic use, agriculture, industry, and the environment [7]. Dams, as one of the most important water resources management structures, play a significant role in water storage, regulation, and distribution. However, the performance of dams is highly dependent on the magnitude and timing of inflow from upstream watersheds. Under climate change conditions, variations in precipitation, increased evapotranspiration, reduced snow storage, and changes in snowmelt timing can alter the inflow regime of dam reservoirs. Therefore, investigating the impacts of climate change on dam inflow is essential for long-term planning and reducing the vulnerability of water resources [4]. Karaj Dam, also known as Amir Kabir Dam, is one of the important dams in Iran for supplying and regulating regional water resources. The upstream watershed of this dam is influenced by climatic variables such as precipitation, temperature, snow, and evaporation. Any changes in these variables can affect the volume of inflow to the dam, the timing of peak and minimum flows, and ultimately the reliability of reservoir operation. Therefore, studying climate change in this watershed can contribute to a better understanding of future water resource conditions and the development of effective management strategies. This study was conducted to evaluate the impacts of climate change on inflow to the Karaj Dam. The roles of changes in temperature, precipitation, and runoff patterns in the upstream watershed of the dam are investigated, and the potential consequences of these changes on the magnitude and timing of inflow are analyzed. Such an analysis can provide a basis for adaptive water resources management, improvement of reservoir operation policies, and reduction of risks associated with drought and climate variability.

Methodology. Considering the selection of three climate models, precipitation and temperature were simulated based on the selected station in the study area under three climate scenarios. In addition, to simulate the inflow to the dam, meteorological and hydrometric station data from the region, as well as the previous period inflow, were used as inputs for predicting future inflow. For this purpose, the LSTM+FHO model was applied to simulate the inflow to the Karaj Dam. The research methodology is presented in Figure (1). To develop an appropriate model for predicting inflow to the dam, the effective parameters were analyzed and introduced into the model under different conditions. The inflow to the dam at time t was defined as the target variable, while the input parameters at time step $t-1$ were considered as predictor variables [8]. The proposed model was simulated on a monthly time scale over a 30-year period. To evaluate and select the most suitable model and predictor variables, the time series data were divided into two sections. In the first section, 80% of the input time series was considered as the training period, while the remaining 20% was used for the validation period. The inflow to the dam was defined based on recorded precipitation values at meteorological stations, river discharge data at hydrometric stations, inflow values from the previous time step, and the corresponding month of the previous year. Figure (2) illustrates the simulation framework for inflow to the Karaj Dam. Considering the locations of meteorological and hydrometric stations in the region (Table 1), seven different scenarios for input variables were considered for the Karaj Dam.

Figure 1. Steps of this research

Figure 2 – Conceptual Model for Simulating Inflow to the Karaj Dam

Artificial Intelligence. The use of artificial intelligence tools as a modern approach for simulating future behavior in water resources studies has expanded considerably and has provided reliable analytical results based on input data time series. Deep learning methods are defined as a subset of machine learning approaches based on artificial neural networks. Deep learning architectures such as deep neural networks, deep belief networks, recurrent neural networks, convolutional neural networks, and transformers have been applied in fields including computer vision, speech recognition, natural language processing, machine translation, bioinformatics, drug design, and medical image analysis. Studies indicate that, in general, three main types of artificial neural networks are used for processing and analysis. Feedforward Neural Networks (FF) are considered the simplest type of neural network. In these networks, information flows only in one direction, from input nodes to output nodes. These networks are commonly used for tasks such as classification, regression, and pattern recognition. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) contain feedback loops that allow them to retain information from previous inputs, making them suitable for tasks such as sequence prediction, language modeling, and speech recognition. Finally, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are designed for processing data with grid-like topologies such as images and videos. These networks use a series of convolutional layers to extract features from input data and are widely used for image recognition, object detection, and video analysis. The Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network includes a feedback loop that enables the storage of information from previous inputs [1]. Therefore, this type of network is suitable for tasks such as sequence prediction, language modeling, and speech recognition. These networks have a recurrent structure in which, at each step, the output from the previous step is combined with new input data and fed back into the network. This loop helps the network preserve previous information alongside new information and generate the desired output accordingly. Such a feature enables the network to effectively process sequential data such as text, audio, and similar datasets. In order to achieve more accurate results, a hybrid approach combining the LSTM simulation method with the FHO optimization technique was employed.

Table 1 – Specifications of Meteorological and Hydrometric Stations

Weather station				Hydrometer station			
ID	UTM X	UTM Y	Name	ID	UTM X	UTM Y	Name
H8	513848	3986373	Sira	W7	528967	3992575	Nesah
H9	529596	3996499	Gachsar	W8	535258	3991221	Gajereh
H10	526846	3985627	Doab	W9	531910	3980781	Shahrestanak
				W10	517692	3988228	Asara
				W11	491000	4004098	Joestan

The Fire Hawk Optimizer (FHO) algorithm was introduced in 2022 by [3]. This algorithm is suitable for simulations under complex nonlinear and non-convex conditions [2]. The algorithm is inspired by the behavior of birds during wildfires, where fire hawks spread burning sticks to unburned areas, forcing other animals to flee and making them easier to hunt [6]. Accordingly, based on an initial random behavior, the initial positions are identified and determined according to Equation (1).

$$X_{ij} = rand * (U_j - L_j) + L_j, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, D \quad (1)$$

In this equation, the values of U_j and L_j represent the upper and lower bounds of the search domain associated with random numbers. Based on each solution X_i , the corresponding fitness value and the best value X_b for each fire source are calculated. Subsequently, the distance between FH and PR is computed according to Equation (2).

$$D_{lk} = \sqrt{(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2}, l = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (2)$$

Subsequently, the value of FH is updated.

$$FH_l(t+1) = FH_l(t) + (r_1 * X_b - r_2 * FH_n(t)), l = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

The value of $FH_n(t)$ represents a fire hawk calculated based on the random values r_1 and r_2 . In addition, the region in which the prey is located is determined using Equation (4).

$$SP_l = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^r PR_q}{r}, q = 1, 2, \dots, r, l = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

Under these conditions, the position of the prey is simulated based on its movement, and its position is determined using Equation (5).

$$PR_q(t+1) = PR_q(t) + (r_3 * FH_l - r_4 * SP_l(t)), l = 1, 2, \dots, n, q = 1, 2, \dots, r \quad (5)$$

Under these conditions, the safe position is updated and determined according to Equation (6).

$$SP = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^m PR_k}{r}, k = 1, 2, \dots, m \quad (6)$$

At this stage, the prey also updates its position.

$$PR_q(t+1) = PR_q(t) + (r_5 * FH_a - r_6 * SP(t)), l = 1, 2, \dots, n, q = 1, 2, \dots, r \quad (7)$$

Climate Change. In this study, three major climate models were investigated:

BCC-CSM2 (Beijing Climate Center Climate System Model Version 2)

This model was developed by the Beijing Climate Center and includes simulations of the atmosphere, ocean, ice, and carbon cycle. It has shown satisfactory performance in predicting precipitation and temperature changes in Asian regions, particularly in Iran and sensitive watershed areas.

MRI-ESM2 (Meteorological Research Institute Earth System Model Version 2)

This model was developed by the Meteorological Research Institute of Japan, with a focus on interactions among the atmosphere, ocean, and carbon cycle. One of its main advantages is its capability to accurately simulate extreme climatic events such as floods and droughts.

CNRM-CM6-1 (Centre National de Recherches Météorologiques Climate Model 6-1)

This model was developed by the National Center for Meteorological Research of France. It is a comprehensive high-resolution model with strong performance in simulating precipitation and temperature across different seasons. The model is suitable for analyzing climate change impacts at medium and small watershed scales.

For each model, SSP were applied to simulate future climate conditions under different levels of economic development and greenhouse gas mitigation or increase:

- SSP1-2.6: A low-emission and sustainable development scenario, leading to limited temperature increase and improved water resource management.

- SSP2-4.5: A moderate-emission scenario representing an intermediate development pathway and moderate climate change impacts on water resources.
- SSP5-8.5: A high-emission scenario associated with rapid economic growth and unrestricted emissions, resulting in significant temperature increases and severe fluctuations in precipitation and river flow.

Results and Discussion. To predict inflow to the dam, statistical analyses were conducted for the Karaj Dam using the LSTM simulation method integrated with the FHO optimization approach, as presented in Table (2). Based on the analyzed time series for the Karaj Dam, the model parameters were evaluated during the training and validation periods. To improve model performance, different combinations of predictor variables were defined and simulated for the Karaj Dam. In order to select the most suitable condition for future prediction, analyses were carried out using statistical indices according to Table (2). Four statistical indicators, including RMSE, MAPE, R^2 , and NASH, were applied for the statistical evaluation. The selection and decision-making process for the optimal model and predictor variables were based on the TEST period results.

Table 2 - Statistical Analysis of Inflow Simulation Results for the Five Drinking Water Supply Dams

Dams	State	Parameters	Train				Test			
			R^2	NASH	RMSE	MAPE	R^2	NASH	RMSE	MAPE
Karaj dam	K1	H8-H9-H10-W7-W8-W9-W10-I	0.84	0.74	5.92	4.17	0.87	0.71	9.6	2.23
	<u>K2</u>	<u>H9-H10-W7-W8-I</u>	<u>0.91</u>	<u>0.88</u>	<u>5.08</u>	<u>2.71</u>	<u>0.9</u>	<u>0.87</u>	<u>4.82</u>	<u>2.97</u>
	K3	H9-H10-W8-W9-I	0.79	0.78	8.52	3.03	0.9	0.83	9.24	1.82
	K4	H10-W8-W9-I	0.88	0.65	7.12	4.9	0.79	0.74	7.76	2.41
	K5	H10-W7-W10	0.76	0.84	5.68	3.2	0.72	0.66	6.88	1.99
	K6	H8-W7-I	0.71	0.67	5.5	4.24	0.89	0.72	9.64	2.49
	K7	H10-W7-I	0.73	0.88	9.64	3.66	0.84	0.87	6.78	3.33

Based on the obtained results, it was found that for the Karaj Dam, the discharge data from the two hydrometric stations, Gachsar (H9) and Doab (H10), represented the best predictor variables, since the main volume of river flow is supplied from these two branches. In addition, the favorable locations of the Gajereh (W8) and Nesa (W7) meteorological stations made them the most suitable meteorological predictor variables. For simulating the impacts of climate change, selecting appropriate climate models is of great importance. Increasing the number of models may increase uncertainty, whereas considering models that provide results consistent with the characteristics of the study area can reduce uncertainty in the results. Accordingly, three climate models, namely BCC-CSM2, MRI-ESM2, and CNRM-CM6-1, were used for the simulations. To prioritize and select these three models for future period simulations, analyses were conducted based on three statistical parameters, including the correlation coefficient, Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and the Kling-Gupta Efficiency (KGE) index, as presented in Table (3). The basis for selecting the most suitable models was the comparison between the simulated baseline period and the observed data.

Table 3 – Statistical Analysis and Prioritization of Climate Models

Parameters	Statistical analysis	<u>BCC-CSM2</u>	<u>MRI-ESM2</u>	<u>CNRM-CM6-1</u>
Rain	Correlation	<u>0.9</u>	<u>0.95</u>	<u>0.91</u>
	RMSE	<u>1.49</u>	<u>1.3</u>	<u>1.48</u>
	KGE	<u>0.88</u>	<u>0.92</u>	<u>0.9</u>
Temperature	Correlation	<u>0.95</u>	<u>0.98</u>	<u>0.97</u>
	RMSE	<u>1.28</u>	<u>1.07</u>	<u>1.27</u>
	KGE	<u>0.92</u>	<u>0.97</u>	<u>0.93</u>
<u>Priority</u>		3	1	2

The computational results presented in Table (3) indicated that, based on observed and historical data, the climate models MRI-ESM2, CNRM-CM6-1, and BCC-CSM2 ranked as the first, second, and third priorities, respectively, for future climate simulations. After evaluating and selecting the three climate models, the performance of the simulation results under the application of three SSP emission scenarios was assessed for two parameters: precipitation and mean temperature during the future period. The future simulation period from 2021 to 2050 was investigated, and downscaling was carried out using the LARS-WG model. The downscaling process was performed for all three emission scenarios. Based on the climate change simulation results and their impacts on temperature and precipitation under future conditions (2021–2050), the inflow to the Karaj Dam was simulated. Figure (3) illustrates the behavior of inflow to the Karaj Dam.

Figure 3 – Prediction of Inflow to the Karaj Dam under Climate Change Conditions

Conclusion. The results of this study demonstrated that the appropriate selection of predictor variables and the hydrological model, including the discharge data from the Gachsar and Doab hydrometric stations as well as the meteorological data from the Gajereh and Nesa stations, has a significant effect on the accuracy of inflow prediction for the Karaj Dam. By evaluating the three climate models MRI-ESM2, CNRM-CM6-1, and BCC-CSM2 under the greenhouse gas emission scenarios SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, and SSP5-8.5, it was found that during the period 2021–2050, the mean temperature is expected to increase while precipitation is projected to decrease, resulting in an approximately 16% reduction in inflow to the dam. This reduction is accompanied by increasing

uncertainty over time and may place significant pressure on drinking water supply, agriculture, and regional water resource management. Therefore, adaptive planning and water resource management strategies are essential in response to climate change impacts.

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SHRINKING GLACIERS, RISING RISK: ASSESSING CLIMATE-DRIVEN WATER STRESS AND ADAPTIVE GOVERNANCE IN CENTRAL ASIA'S TRANSBOUNDARY RIVER BASINS

Abstract. *This article analyzes the escalating water crisis in Central Asia's transboundary basins, where rapid glacial melt meets fragmented governance. The Aral Sea's 90% volume loss signals a hydrological emergency now accelerated by climate change. As the Tien Shan and Pamir glaciers-the source of 40–50% of regional runoff-have retreated nearly 30% since 1960, the region approaches a "peak water" tipping point: a transient melt surge followed by permanent, irreversible decline. Bridging the gap between glaciology and policy, this study links physical hydrological stress to institutional adaptive capacity. It evaluates historical trends since 1960, the adequacy of current multilateral frameworks, and strategies to close governance gaps. By utilizing remote sensing to analyze glaciation and runoff trends, the paper performs a systematic stress-test of existing institutions and provides evidence-based policy recommendations tailored to the regional transboundary context.*

Keywords: *Glacier retreat; peak water; transboundary water management; Central Asia; Amu Darya; climate-induced water scarcity; institutional adaptive capacity; hydrological vulnerability; Aral Sea crisis; remote sensing.*

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